

The Status of Positive Psychology Strengths within the Romanian School in the Digital Society

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to identify the possible correlations between the strengths that are taught in school and those which are necessary for reaching personal success. In order to test the extent to which these strengths correlate, we applied a psychological-assessment tool composed of 24 strengths with a Likert-type response scale. The subjects selected for this research were 100 teachers from Romania, both male and female. The results were processed in SPSS Statistics, where we also calculated Pearson's correlation coefficient. After analyzing the descriptive statistics and the correlation coefficient we noticed that the "Vitality" strength showed a statistically significant negative correlation between the two groups, therefore it is not taught in school but it is considered important for achieving personal success. The "Citizenship" strength showed a statistically significant positive correlation, being concurrently promoted in school and important in achieving success.

The neuro-linguistic reprogramming of a young individual will need a considerable effort, first of all as regards being aware of the values which render his well-being, and secondly as regards his orientation towards these values, which as it seems he was not at all oriented to. The new student profile of today's society, also known as the digital native, needs to assimilate a full set of positive psychology values in order to create a complete model of success for nowadays' world.

Keywords: school, strengths, success, positive psychology, neuropsychology, neuro-linguistic programming, digital native.

1. Introduction

According to Caine et.al., the functions of brain structures represent a field of interest for both psychologists and neuroscientists, since a series of learning principles, which are commonly associated with neuroscience, can likewise be assigned to the development of students' learning, interacting and processing information (Caine et al., 2005; Goswami, 2008). At the same time, the area of neuroscience which focuses on brain mechanisms promotes what is known as neuro-linguistics, along with one of its specific functions – neuro-linguistic programming (NLP). NLP is tightly connected to education (Norman, 2000), as it provides a model of cognitive and behavioral mechanisms, which are concurrently linked to the nervous system and the brain and to the

improvement of our interaction and affiliation with others (Bandler & Grinder, 1979). Moreover, interaction, intention, passion, imagination, self-awareness, affiliation – they “all represent a kind of interface between how we relate with each other, how we would like to be ourselves and how we finally achieve self-fulfillment” (Hertenstein, & Weiss, 2011, p. 4).

The digital society we live in, also referred to as the information society, is driven by information and communication technologies which allow people to produce and share data unboundedly (Webster, 2006). This digital society has a visible impact upon the educational process as well, as it has given birth to a new student profile – the digital native (Prensky, 2001), a type of student who cannot see the world other than digital (Abraham & Behrendt, 2010). In Tapscott’s opinion, digital natives guide themselves according to eight standards derived from their permanent contact with technology: freedom, customization, scrutiny, integrity, collaboration, entertainment, speed and innovation (Tapscott, 2009). When these standards are confronted with the 24 character strengths regarded by this study, we can notice an obvious similarity between the standards mentioned and values like: creativity, integrity, vitality, fairness, citizenship, or humor. What happens though with the rest of the values which the digital native might not have? In this situation, it becomes of clear necessity to think about how school can at the same time meet the student’s needs and provide him with the values that he lacks, in order to create a complete and integrative student profile.

Another essential concept in neuroscience with a great impact on positive psychology is “self-directed neuroplasticity”, a principle according to which methodical effort and exercise can reshape cerebral function in an expected manner and with a curative purpose (Schwartz & Strach, 1991). Apart from the deliberate neuroplasticity, it seems that digital natives go through this process even without noticing. Brain reorganization only occurs when attention is directed to a certain sensory input for a long time. In order for this reorganization to occur there are usually necessary 100 minute sessions, 5 days a week, for 50-10 weeks (Bruer, 1999), precisely what digital natives do today when playing video games or browsing online (Eduardsen, 2001). Nonetheless, in terms of positive psychology through deliberate neuroplasticity, this principle allowed Shapiro and Carlson to state that the more we exercise positive thinking and self-compassion, the more we help our neurons to develop new connections and to strengthen that specific area of our brain. This conversion in our brain eventually leads to changing our set point of happiness (Shapiro & Carlson, 2009).

However, the values of positive thinking are not always what we choose to exercise. What we impose to ourselves or what is imposed to us by others can be both positive and negative. According to Beck’s cognitive theory, distress finds its origins in the contradiction between the demands imposed by others or self-imposed (by means of self-programming) and the individual’s abilities and resorts (Beck, et al., 2005). Parenthetically, self-programming appears whenever an individual envisions how he/she might behave in a certain context, according to his experience up to that moment, thus creating a mental model which is ready to be used in a future real situation (Korkmaz, 2013). Returning to positive and negative emotions, cognitive-behaviorists state that both of them are the result of the individual’s cognitions (David, 2006), although they can be altered through the constant training framed by neuroplasticity.

What is presumably considered the need to create a definite joint between neuroscience, positive psychology and neuropsychology led to the formation of a new field of study known as “positive neuropsychology”. According to Randolph, neuropsychology, which refers to the study and development of cognitive health, added with the principles of positive psychology, forms the boundaries of positive neuropsychology. Under these circumstances, positive neuropsychology depicts “an overarching orientation to our work that emphasizes cognitive wellness” (Randolph, 2013, p. 3), in other words the orientation that emphasizes the very same values of positive psychology developed by Seligman and pointed out in this study.

We started from the premise that we need to identify how many prevalent virtues of positive psychology are actually internalized within the educational process in school, as it is one of the key

elements at the basis of our students' development. Later on, as a latter part of this research, we could focus our attention on developing a specific setup of neurolinguistics programming for internalizing these values.

As regards the contemporary positive psychology, Peterson and Park noted that it holds a double input: on the one hand, it provides an umbrella term for the theory and research that have been so far secluded and, on the other hand, it provides the consistent argument that what makes life worth living should earn its own field of study within psychology (Peterson & Park, 2008: 85).

Within the studies of positive psychology, the concept under discussion has been many a time associated with well-being. "Positive Psychology is concerned with the pleasant life, the engaged life and the meaningful life. These three orientations to happiness are associated with well-being." (Carr, 2011: 2) Nonetheless, we tend to disagree with a very strict boundary line between the elements that influence and form personal well-being. According to Magnusson and Cairns' holistic paradigm, an individual must be perceived as an "organized whole", rather than a sum of singular aspects which have been analyzed separately (Magnusson & Cairns, 1996 in Pilkauskaitė-Valickienė, & Gabrielaviciute, 2014). Therefore, in studying students' satisfaction as a whole, there is a series of elements which should be taken into consideration simultaneously. For instance, O'Brien states that "school climate and school culture, what is taught and how it is assessed and the relationships between students and teachers must be analyzed in order to develop educational programs that are focused not only on academic success, but on also on the students' well-being" (Nevogan, 2013: 200).

Aside from this resemblance to well-being, positive psychology has developed a series of concepts, usually referred to as "strengths" that are thought to improve an individual's life quality and provide him with the necessary assets for gaining success. For instance, researchers and psychologists who focused on positive psychology in the matter of prevention discovered "which are the specific strengths that are necessary for protecting the individual from a mental illness: courage, future-oriented thinking, optimism, interpersonal skills, faith, work ethic, hope, honesty, perseverance and the ability to develop insights" (Seligman, Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). Alongside the aforementioned strengths, there are also other concepts that may be included in the field of positive psychology, such as: life satisfaction, self-concept, optimism and self-efficacy.

In point of life satisfaction, this concept was defined as "an individual's overall appraisals of the quality of his or her life" (Diener, Emmons, Larsen & Griffin, 1985 in Chen et al., 2016: 105). Life satisfaction, as the individual's perspective on life, can many a time be influenced by self-esteem, which, in its turn, can be influenced by the individual's socioeconomic status (SES). In this case, self-esteem serves as a mediator between life satisfaction and SES, which represents the way society is related to the individual (Twenge & Campbell, 2002). Beside this viewpoint, we also support Sagone and De Caroli's opinion according to which apart from an individual's socioeconomic status, self-esteem is equally related to self-determination and independence (Sagone, De Caroli, 2014), in other words, the extent to which an individual is able to control his own thoughts and act accordingly. In 2005, Lent et al. put forward an integrative model of well-being and psychosocial adjustment which included personality traits and affective dispositions, life satisfaction, self-efficacy and environmental supports and resources. In their opinion, the simplest way to achieve life satisfaction is through domain satisfaction, in other words, through achieving success in a specific area of life, such as school. In their study, "domain satisfaction was found to be the single most consistent predictor of overall life satisfaction" (Lent et al., 2005: 439) while the development of a positive self-system throughout a teenager's school education was proved to play an important role in creating a positive life course trajectory (Patrick et al., 2007; Shanahan, 2000).

Self-concept is considered imperative for maximizing human potential, from its early stages, such as school achievement, up to physical/mental well-being, productive employment and other contributions to society (Craven, Marsh & Burnett, 2003 apud Martin, 2006: 312).

In terms of optimism, Friedman and Kern regard it as a tendency of having positive expectations for the future and for being confident in one's ability to deal with challenges (Friedman & Kern, 2014). Scheier, Carver, and Bridges (2001) define optimism as "expectancies that are

generalized—expectancies that pertain more or less to the individual's entire life space" (apud Feldman & Kubota, 2015: 211). In Europe, the relationship between optimism and health was confirmed by a Finnish study which involved 8.690 middle-aged subjects. Optimism and extroversion correlated with healthy lifestyle in samples of English, Belgian, Finnish and Norwegian young adults. Another Polish-Swedish research team found correlations between a healthy behaviour and optimism, self-efficacy and the sense of coherence (Dosedlova et al., 2014:1053).

Self-efficacy, an equally important element in positive psychology, was regarded by Bandura as "concerned with judgments of how well one can execute courses of action required to deal with prospective situations" (1982, apud Locke & Johnston, 2016: 1). Bandura (1977) also compared self-efficacy with expectancies of goal outcomes: "Outcome and efficacy expectations are differentiated, because individuals can believe that a particular course of action will produce certain outcomes, but if they entertain serious doubts about whether they can perform the necessary activities, such information does not influence their behaviour" (apud Feldman & Kubota, 2015: 211). In school, teacher efficacy, regarded as the confidence held by teachers in terms of personal and collective ability to influence student learning, represents a key motivator in enhancing students' development (Klassen et al., 2011: 21). This point of view is also supported by Zimmerman who states that self-efficacy is "the judgement of an individual about how well he is able to make something come true and succeed at the end" (apud Saricoban, 2015). It is imperative to mention that we concurrently advocate a more integrative viewpoint, according to which parent-child relations are as important as teacher efficacy in developing students' motivation (Grigoryeva & Shamionov, 2014). However, we have focused our attention on the latter one, as it is strongly related to the subject under study.

1. Methodology

2.1. Aim

The aim of our research is to identify a possible correlation between the strengths taught in school and those which are necessary for achieving personal success.

2.2. Hypothesis

There is a statistically significant correlation between the strengths taught in school and the strengths that ensure personal success.

2.3. Subjects

The participants were 100 teachers from Romania, aged between 20-60, both male and female, from sciences and humanities.

2.4. Method

For the present research we used a tool composed of 24 strengths: creativity, curiosity, open-mindedness, love of learning, perspective, bravery, persistence, integrity, vitality, love, kindness, social intelligence, citizenship, fairness, leadership, forgiveness and mercy, modesty, prudence, self-regulation, appreciation of beauty and excellence, gratitude, hope, humor and spirituality. We used a Likert-type response scale from 0 to 5, where 0 = not important, 1 = slightly important, 2 = moderately important, 3 = important, 4 = fairly important and 5 = very important.

The participants were given the necessary instructions before completing the questionnaire.

In 2004, Seligman and Peterson (apud Seligman & Peterson, 2005) developed a list of 6 virtues and 24 related character strengths.

Character Strengths	
Wisdom and Knowledge	Creativity Curiosity Open-mindedness Love of learning Perspective
Courage	Bravery Persistence Integrity Vitality
Humanity	Love Kindness Social Intelligence
Justice	Citizenship Fairness Leadership
Temperance	Forgiveness and mercy Modesty Prudence Self-regulation
Transcendence	Appreciation of beauty and excellence Gratitude Hope Humor Spirituality

1. Results

The results were introduced and processed in SPSS Statistics. In order to identify the level of correlation for all the selected strengths, we applied descriptive statistics and Pearson's correlation test. The descriptive statistics for the questionnaire results, Pearson's correlation coefficient and two Pie Chart graphs are presented hereinafter.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for the 24 strengths

	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
creativitysuccess	100	388.00	3.8800	1.32787
curiositysuccess	100	325.00	3.2500	1.47966
openmindednesssucces	100	316.00	3.1600	1.35378
succes	100	302.00	3.0200	1.46322
perpectivesucces	100	347.00	3.4700	1.49379
braverysucces	100	195.00	1.9500	1.86068
persistencesucces	100	369.00	3.6900	1.46815
integritysucces	100	298.00	2.9800	1.44236
vitalitysucces	100	268.00	2.6800	1.60731
lovesucces	100	236.00	2.3600	1.53426
kindnesssucces	100	227.00	2.2700	1.72829

socialintelligence	100	342.00	3.4200	1.41550
citizenshipsucces	100	123.00	1.2300	1.58181
fairnesssucces	100	300.00	3.0000	1.46336
leadershipsucces	100	181.00	1.8100	1.64344
forgivenessandmercysucces	100	165.00	1.6500	1.38808
modestysucces	100	196.00	1.9600	1.66315
prudencesucces	100	222.00	2.2200	1.51478
selfregulationsucces	100	296.00	2.9600	1.43492
appreciationofbeautyandexcellencesuccess	100	199.00	1.9900	1.39621
gratitudesucces	100	172.00	1.7200	1.45699
hopesucces	100	251.00	2.5100	1.64835
humorsucces	100	210.00	2.1000	1.69074
spiritualitysucces	100	163.00	1.6300	1.72712
creativityschool	100	268.00	2.6800	1.67501
curiositieschool	100	277.00	2.7700	1.61342
openmindednessschool	100	347.00	3.4700	1.69047
loveoflearningschool	100	320.00	3.2000	1.68775
perspectiveschool	100	235.00	2.3500	1.55943
braveryschool	100	169.00	1.6900	1.38312
perseverenceschool	100	356.00	3.5600	1.56554
integrityschool	100	254.00	2.5400	1.52700
vitalityschool	100	196.00	1.9600	1.55648
loveschool	100	210.00	2.1000	1.54069
kindnessschool	100	204.00	2.0400	1.42786
socialintelligenceschool	100	277.00	2.7700	1.46925
citizenshpschool	100	253.00	2.5300	1.57925
fairnessschool	100	304.00	3.0400	1.43492
leadershpschool	100	179.00	1.7900	1.60991
forgivenessandmercyschool	100	188.00	1.8800	1.67139
modestyschool	100	227.00	2.2700	1.85785
prudenceschool	100	268.00	2.6800	1.47628
selfregulationschool	100	244.00	2.4400	1.78275
appreciationofbeauty andexcellenceschool	100	274.00	2.7400	1.62443
gratitudeschool	100	227.00	2.2700	1.52325
hopeschool	100	179.00	1.7900	1.48593
humorschool	100	139.00	1.3900	1.54981
spiritualitieschool	100	137.00	1.3700	1.41888
Valid N (listwise)	100			

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of this study: the number of subjects, sum, mean and standard deviation. Most of the response means for the strengths that are necessary in achieving personal success were higher than those for the strengths promoted in school. Hence, we can assume that within the Romanian school, some of these 24 strengths, such as Creativity (mean success = 3.8, mean school = 2.6), Vitality (mean success = 2.6, mean school = 1.9) and Social Intelligence (mean success = 3.4, mean school = 2.7) have lower values than those necessary for achieving personal success. These results imply that our educational process is in need of a change which should start with reprioritizing the strengths promoted in school.

As stated above, there is a discrepancy between Creativity as a goal and what actually happens in school. Even though a teacher might feel the need of developing this personality trait, the curriculum design does not allow him to be flexible enough. Thus, we are currently facing an imperative need of implementing more programs for personal development and more classes which allow students to create original products.

Table 2. Correlation Vitality

Correlations			
		Vitality success	Vitality school
Vitality success	Pearson Correlation	1	-.774
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.044
	N	100	100
Vitality school	Pearson Correlation	-.774	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.044	
	N	100	100

Table 2 illustrates the correlation between "Vitality" as strength necessary for achieving personal success and "Vitality" as strength promoted in school. A statistically significant negative correlation (-.774) can be noticed between these two elements. Therefore, Vitality, defined as "approaching life with excitement and energy; feeling alive and activated" is not properly cultivated in school, although it is generally regarded as being highly important in achieving personal success.

Optimizing this personality trait in school might increase the students' level of self-satisfaction. What a teacher could actually do at school is to help students develop a dynamic and proactive attitude.

Table 3. Correlation Citizenship

Correlations			
		Citizenshipsuccess	Citizenshipschool
Citizenshipsuccess	Pearson Correlation	1	.769
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.037
	N	100	100
Citizenshipschool	Pearson Correlation	.769	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.037	
	N	100	100

Table 3 illustrates the correlation between "Citizenship" as an imperative strength in achieving personal success and "Citizenship" as strength taught in school. A statistically significant positive correlation (.769) can be noticed between these two elements. In this case, Citizenship, defined as "working well as a member of a group or team; being loyal to the group", is both cultivated in school and regarded as very important in achieving personal success.

Thus, if we teach students to develop a socially responsible behaviour, their perception on loyalty within a group will naturally improve in time. Being responsible becomes a more and more valuable trait, both socially and individually, and it has to be cultivated particularly by teachers.

Figure 1. Pie chart vitalitysuccess

Figure 2. Pie chart vitalityschool

The Pie charts above illustrate the distribution of responses for the "Vitality" strength. It can be noticed how the lower values are much more frequent than the high ones, in terms of promoting this strength in school. Thus, the participants at this study consider that school does not attach enough importance to this strength, even though it has proven to be so mandatory in assuring the students' well-being and personal success.

Considering our initial hypothesis, we can state that it was not confirmed, as it did not exist a statistically significant correlation for the 24 strengths, between what is promoted in school and

what is considered to be necessary for achieving personal success. The Romanian educational system should reconsider the values taught in school, as they do not concord with the real necessities for achieving personal success.

2. Conclusions

A positive school climate can help solve a series of educational issues, affecting both the teacher's and the student's behaviour. A supportive school climate was confirmed to positively affect teachers' self-efficacy, to manifest a long-term positive effect on student learning and to encourage personal well-being (Ciani et al., 2008). Along with all these favourable outcomes, researchers found that a positive school climate also develops a sense of belonging, trust, care and respect, common beliefs and values, as well as cooperation and responsibility. (Meristo & Eisenschmidt, 2014). Each of the aforementioned effects is essential for ensuring a productive school environment, governed by mutual agreement, partnership and cohesiveness. Unfortunately at this very moment we are unable to talk about a fundamental orientation of the young people towards the values which, if they guided their lives, would lead them to a general state of well-being and would keep them aloof from depression, alienation or other counterproductive psychological conditions. What is undoubtedly necessary for reaching a positive outcome in this field of action is being aware of all these values under discussion and following a guided process of neurolinguistics programming. So again it is imperative to reflect upon the way in which school can help build a young person's profile and offer him all the necessary values for developing a unitary and integrative model of success for today's society.

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Annex no.1. The 22 strengths

Table 4. Correlation Creativity

	Creativity success	Creativity school
creativitysuccess	1	-.071
	Pearson Correlation	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.589
	N	100
creativityschool	-.071	1
	Pearson Correlation	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.589
	N	100

Table 5. Correlation Curiosity

	curiositysuccess	curiosityschool
Curiosity success	1	-.035
	Pearson Correlation	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.592
	N	100
Curiosity school	-.035	1
	Pearson Correlation	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.592
	N	100

Table 6. Correlation Openmindedness

		open-mindedness success	open-mindedness school
open-mindedness success	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 100	-.068 .608 100
open-mindedness school	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-.068 .608 100	1 100

Table 7. Correlation Love of learning

		Love of learning success	Love of learning school
Love of learning success	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 100	.197 .131 100
Love of learning school	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.197 .131 100	1 100

Table 8. Correlation Perspective

		Perspective success	Perspective school
perspectivesuccess	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 100	-.068 .608 100
perspectiveschool	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-.068 .608 100	1 100

Table 9. Correlation Bravery

	braverysuccess	braveryschool
braverysuccess	1	.004
	Pearson Cor	.577
	Sig. (2-tailed)	100
	N	1
braveryschool	.004	1
	Pearson Cor	.577
	Sig. (2-tailed)	100
	N	100

Table 10. Correlation Persistence

	persistenceesuccess	persistenceeschool
persistenceesuccess	1	.075
	Pearson Correlation	.571
	Sig. (2-tailed)	100
	N	1
persistenceeschool	.075	1
	Pearson Correlation	.571
	Sig. (2-tailed)	100
	N	100

Table 11. Correlation Integrity

	Integrity success	Integrity school
Integrity success	1	.058
	Pearson Correlation	.661
	Sig. (2-tailed)	100
	N	1
Integrity school	.058	1
	Pearson Correlation	.661
	Sig. (2-tailed)	100
	N	100

Table 12. Correlation Love

	Love success	Love school
Love success	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 .117 100
Love school	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.117 .373 100

Table 13. Correlation Kindness

	kindness success	kindness school
Kindness success:	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 .591 100
Kindness school	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-.071 .591 100

Table 14. Correlation Social Intelligence

	Social intelligence success	Social intelligence school
Social intelligence success	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 .047 100
Social intelligence school	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.047 .722 100

Table 15. Correlation Fairness

	Fairness success	Fairness school
Fairness success	1	
	Pearson Correlation	-.015
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.912
	N	100
Fairness school		1
	Pearson Correlation	-.015
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.912
	N	100

Table 16. Correlation Leadership

	Leadership success	Leadership school
Leadership success	1	
	Pearson Correlation	-.130
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.320
	N	100
Leadership school		1
	Pearson Correlation	-.130
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.320
	N	100

Table 17. Correlation Forgiveness and Mercy

	Forgiveness and mercy success	Forgiveness and mercy school
Forgiveness and mercy success	1	
	Pearson Correlation	.012
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.330
	N	100
Forgiveness and mercy school		1
	Pearson Correlation	.012
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.330
	N	100

Table 18. Correlation Modesty

	Modesty success	Modesty school
Modesty success	1	-.005
	Pearson Correlation	.469
	Sig. (2-tailed)	100
	N	1
Modesty school	-.005	1
	Pearson Correlation	.469
	Sig. (2-tailed)	100
	N	100

Table 19. Correlation Prudence

	Prudence success	Prudence school
Prudence success	1	-.227
	Pearson Correlation	.081
	Sig. (2-tailed)	100
	N	1
Prudence school	-.227	1
	Pearson Correlation	.081
	Sig. (2-tailed)	100
	N	100

Table 20. Correlation Self-regulation

	self-regulation success	self-regulation school
self-regulation success	1	.085
	Pearson Correlation	.519
	Sig. (2-tailed)	100
	N	1
self-regulation school	.085	1
	Pearson Correlation	.519
	Sig. (2-tailed)	100
	N	100

Table 21. Correlation Appreciation of beauty and excellence

	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	Appreciation of beauty and excellence succes	Appreciation of beauty and excellence school
Appreciation of beauty and excellence succes	1 100	1 100	-.029 .524 100
Appreciation of beauty and excellence school	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-.029 .524 100	1 100

Table 22. Correlation Gratitude

	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	Gratitude succes:	Gratitude school
Gratitude succes	1 100	1 100	.045 .732 100
Gratitude school	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.045 .732 100	1 100

Table 23. Correlation Hope

	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	Hope succes	Hope school
Hope succes	1 100	1 100	.036 .286 100
Hope school	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.036 .286 100	1 100

Table 24. Correlation Humor

		Humor success	Humor school
Humor succes	Pearson Correlation	1	.160
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.222
	N	100	100
Humor school	Pearson Correlation	.160	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.222	
	N	100	100

Table 25. Correlation Spirituality

		Spirituality success	Spirituality school
Spirituality success	Pearson Correlation	1	.107
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.416
	N	100	100
Spirituality school	Pearson Correlation	.107	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.416	
	N	100	100